

Study on the catalytic synthetic preparation of rubber anti-oxidant 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydro-quinoline polymer

Yu Liu^{a,b*}, Qingyu Gao^a, Lianxin Liu^b and Shuting Li^b

^aCollege of Chemistry and Engineering Technology, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou 221116, China

^bXuzhou College of Industrial and Technology, Jiangsu Xuzhou 221140, China

E-mail : liuyu0138@163.com

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Abstract : The paper is on the catalytic synthetic preparation of production of a rubber anti-oxidant 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydro-quinoline polymer ((C₁₂H₁₅N)_n, n = 2-4 RD). The process uses one step and solvent-free preparation of RD, without using hydrochloric acid as a catalyst. A solid resin is used as a catalyst and recycling method followed. Use of the process increases the effective concentration of RD (the content of dimer, trimer and tetramer of RD) from 46 to 75%. No waste water is produced and environmental pollution has been controlled.

Keywords : Rubber antioxidant, RD catalyst, solid resin.

Introduction

Rubber anti-oxidant 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydro-quinoline polymer, (C₁₂H₁₅N)_n, n = 2-4 (RD)^{1,2} is a ketone amine antioxidant. It performs excellently in protection from oxidation of rubber which is caused by thermal oxidative aging and catalytic oxidation by metal ions. RD is mainly used for natural rubber and chloroprene rubber etc. It has excellent effects on the ageing caused by heating and oxygen, and has stronger restrained effect on the metallic catalysis and oxidation. It is mainly used in natural rubber, synthetic rubber and latex.

There is no influence on the processing properties of rubber, curing characteristics and physical properties of vulcanizates while adding RD. RD is a mixture consisting essentially of monomer, dimer, trimer and more highly polymerized products.

RD results from the condensation reaction of aniline with acetone in the presence of a condensation catalyst such as hydrochloric acid for traditional manufacturing processes. The monomeric material is first formed by the reaction but the rate of the condensation reaction is quite slow compared to the rate at which the monomeric material polymerizes.

There are two methods of synthesizing RD at present. One is a "two-step process"³, the equipment investment is too expensive for the long technical process in this method. The other method is a "one-step process"; the catalyst used in this process (BF₃ etc.) is expensive. RD is not only superior in preventing heat aging but also cheaply available. The temperature of salify reaction for aniline with catalyst (such as hydrochloric acid) is about 120-150 °C and temperature of condensation for reaction with acetone is more than 140 °C. In this study, the "one-step process and solvent-free preparation of rubber antioxidant RD" with the catalyst of solid resin is followed. The content of RD is the inspection target, using the orthogonal design method. The ratio of keto-amine, reaction time, reaction temperature, resin-amine ratio were the inspection factors.

Experimental

Materials and equipment :

Acetone and aniline were analytically pure. Solid cation exchange resin and HPLC-grade methanol was used. Hitachi L-2000 HPLC inclusion auto-sampler L-2200, organizer, UV-Vis detector L-2420 (200-900 nm), pump L-2130, chromatographic column Shimadzu C18 4.6 mm

× 150 mm/5 μm, Satorious electronic balance B204-N (Max 210 g; d = 0.1 mg), ultrasound cleaner, vacuum rotating evaporation apparatus and vacuum pump etc. were used.

Principle of reaction and production process :

The acetone and aniline reaction with solid resin as catalyst is shown in Fig. 1. RD polymer containing a large amount of RD dimer has exhibited markedly superior performance. The product quality depended on the content of dimer. The content of RD polymer is about 40 wt% to 50 wt%. The process has three stages as shown in Fig. 2.

(i) The resin is soaked in 10–15% hydrochloric acid for 5 to 6 h. The reactions are salify reaction, condensation reaction and polymerization reaction. The temperature of the reaction and the amount of acetone, aniline and front fraction should be controlled. The mode of addition of acetone is very important (~4 h). Solid resin and aniline ratio is about 1 : 0.1–0.15 (wt%). The solid resin was removed by screening. Next the front fraction and a small amount hydrochloric acid (about 5% by mass of aniline, concentration 36.0%) was added to the reactor.

(ii) A small amount sodium hydroxide solution was added to the reaction solution and the pH was adjusted between 7 and 9.

(iii) The products were separated from unreacted material (aniline) and solvent (acetone) by reduced pressure distillation. Unreacted materials, solvent and RD monomer (named front fraction) were recycled to the reactor.

To a 1000 mL 3-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, a thermometer and a reflux condenser, 250 mL aniline, 100 mL acetone and 50 g NRW solid resin were added. The time of salify reaction is about 2 h. After filtering the solid resin 150 mL front fraction and 10 mL hydrochloric acid were added and the reaction temperature was raised to about 110 °C. Acetone was added slowly for condensation reaction and the temperature was allowed to rise to 135 °C. Addition of sodium hydroxide solution followed by reduced pressure distillation (150–380 °C) and cooling gave the end product RD.

Optimization of the process⁶⁻¹¹ :

In the production of RD, salify reaction temperature, condensation reaction temperature and time, and the ratio

Fig. 1. Steps of reaction.

Fig. 2. Preparation of rubber anti-oxidant RD using of solid resin catalyst.

of keto-amine are key factors. Orthogonal experimental design determines the optimum reaction conditions. Level factors are shown in Table 1. A is the ratio of keto-amine, B is the time of condensation reaction, C is the

Table 1. Factors and level of $L_9 (3^4)$

Level	Factor			
	A (mole/mole)	B (time/h)	C (°C)	D (°C)
1	1.5	3.5	115-120	90
2	2.0	4.0	120-125	95
3	2.5	4.5	125-130	100

temperature of condensation reaction and D is the temperature of salify reaction.

Test method of content of rubber anti-oxidant RD :

For the composition of complex samples, it is difficult

to get good separation using a chromatographic system.

The method of gradient elution by methanol HPLC

Table 2. Gradient composition of mobile phase

Time (min)	Methanol (%)	Water (%)
0	65	35
10	65	35
20	75	25
30	85	15
40	90	10
50	95	5
60	95	5
70	100	0
80	100	0

grade and water was followed. Gradient composition of mobile phase is shown in Table 2.

Preparation of test solution : About 1.5 mg of rubber anti-oxidant RD was weighed accurately in a 10 mL volumetric flask with methanol.

Procedure :

20 µL of system suitability solution was injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded up to 80 min. The concentration of related substances was calculated by area normalization method. HPLC chromatogram of RD is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. HPLC chromatogram of RD : (A) Dimer, (B) Trimer, (C) Tetramer.

Experimental results :

Table 3 shows the content of dimer, trimer and tetramer. Orthogonal test showed that the ratio of the reaction temperature significantly affects the content, followed by the ratio keto-amine, reaction time and catalyst acid-amine. The result shows that $A_2B_3C_2D_2$ has a significant effect on the reaction. The ratio of keto-amine was 2.0 (mole/mole), the reaction time was 4.5 h, the reaction temperature was 120–125 °C and the temperature of salify reaction was 95 °C. Optimized conditions were used in the production and testing 6 was made in batches. The results are shown in Table 5. The content of rubber anti-oxidant RD is more than 60% (wt%). The reaction has improved content of dimer, trimer and tetramer while the content of the dimer is more than 40%. Tests of between-subject's effects by spss12.0 have been shown in Table 4.

Discussion

The process of producing RD using hydrochloric acid

Table 3. Result from the orthogonal test of uniform design for manufacture process of RD

Sl. no.	Level				Content (%)
	A	B	C	D	
1.	1	1	1	1	46.50
2.	1	2	2	2	65.35
3.	1	3	3	3	60.35
4.	2	1	2	3	63.45
5.	2	2	3	1	61.35
6.	2	3	1	2	68.35
7.	3	1	3	2	45.75
8.	3	2	1	3	48.40
9.	3	3	2	1	66.20
\bar{I}_j	57.400	51.900	54.417	58.017	
\bar{II}_j	64.383	58.367	65.000	59.817	
\bar{III}_j	53.450	64.967	55.817	57.400	
R	10.933	13.067	10.583	2.417	

Table 4. Tests of between-subjects effects

Dependent variable : Content of RD

Source	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	638.323 ^a	6	106.387	22.491	0.043
Intercept	30706.721	1	30706.721	6491.526	0.000
Acetone ratio of aniline	183.907	2	91.954	19.439	0.049
Time of reaction	256.116	2	128.058	27.072	0.036
Temperature of reaction	198.301	2	99.150	20.961	0.046
Error	9.461	2	4.730		
Total	31354.505	9			
Corrected total	647.784	8			

^aR squared = 0.985 (adjusted R squared = 0.942).

Table 5. Content of rubber anti-oxidant RD

Sl. no.	Dimer (%)	Trimer (%)	Tetramer (%)	Total (%)
1.	43.50	15.38	6.45	65.33
2.	46.20	14.86	6.20	67.26
3.	43.18	15.20	5.80	64.18
4.	44.35	14.95	5.95	65.25
5.	46.15	15.65	5.60	67.40
6.	43.80	14.50	5.45	63.75

in the traditional way is shown in Fig. 4. In the present process using solid resin as catalyst, hydrochloric acid is required in small amount and so sodium hydroxide solution is also small. Washing with water is not necessary in

Fig. 4. Production of rubber anti-oxidant RD catalyst hydrochloric acid catalyst.

this case. Moreover the traditional process temperature of salify reaction is 130 °C but the salify reaction by solid resin at not more than 100 °C. Water largely affects the progress of polymerization, and therefore must be removed in the traditional process. In the process using solid resin as catalyst the content of RD is more than 60% with content of dimer more than 40%.

During the condensation (polymerization), addition of the front fraction is very important. The result of the analysis of front fraction is shown in Fig. 5.

It should be noted that this study has only examined factors and levels of the ratio of keto-amine, the time and temperature of the condensation reaction and the temperature of salify reaction.

Fig. 5. HPLC chromatogram of front fraction : (A) aniline, (B) monomer, (C) dimer.

References

1. Cyril A. Migdal and Ronald D. Abbott, U.S. Patent 6,726,855 B1 (2004).
2. Takashi Kojima and Ryoza Ishimoto, US Patent 4,326,062 (1982).
3. Monsanto Chemical Company, Method of making improved polymeric di-hydroquinoline compositions [P], US : 3047521, 1962-07-31.
4. B. F. Goodrich Company, Improvements in or relating to aniline condensation products and process of preparing same [P], GB : 620314, 1949-05-23.
5. B F Goodrich Company, Preparation of monomeric 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-di-hydroquinoline [P], US : 2514648, 1950-06-11.
6. Institute Organicheskoi Khimii Imeni N. D. Zelinskogo An SSSR, Process for the production of substituted 1,2-dihydroquinolines [P], GB : 1256725, 1971-12-15.
7. R. M. Acheson, "An Introduction to the Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds [M]", 1st ed., Interscience Publishers Inc, London, 1962, pp. 223-227.
8. Heliodoro Monroy Rivera, Novel apparatus for the obtention of substituted 1,2-dihydroquinolines [P], US : 3829292, 1974-08-13.
9. Heliodoro Monroy Rivera, Novel apparatus for the obtention of substituted 1,2-dihydroquinolines [P], US : 3907507, 1975-09-23.
10. I. W. Elliott and H. C. Dunathan, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 833.
11. B. F. Goodrich, Antioxidant [P], US : 2048822, 1936-07-28.

